

Blended Learning And Its Effect On Diversified Students Achievement Under The Background of Higher Vocational Enrollment Expansion

Hua Tian, Yanjun Song

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Abstract

The successive higher education expansion policies in 2019 and 2020 have prompted adult social students to enter higher education institutions that were originally mainly full-time off-the-job. Given that the diversified student population after the expansion also assumes social roles, higher vocational education as academic education has both the implication of adult education. In view of the learning characteristics required by adult roles and the application of new digital technologies in education, blended learning becomes an important and necessary form of teaching and learning for the cultivation of diverse students. However, there are few studies on the impact of teaching behaviors on learning inputs and learning outcomes in blended learning environments, especially in the field of adult education. This study constructs a model of the effect of blended learning on teaching behavior-learning engagement-learning effectiveness for diverse students, and validates the theoretical model by conducting a questionnaire survey on 2,132 students enrolled in the blended learning environment. The results showed that both teachers' teaching behaviors and students' learning inputs positively influenced learning outcomes in a blended learning environment, and teachers' teaching attitudes, teaching preparation, and teaching contexts positively contributed to students' cognitive, affective, and behavioral inputs, respectively. In addition, the effects of teaching behaviors on the dimensions of learning engagement were more pronounced among diverse students with higher motivation and self-efficacy. In order to promote the blended learning model to play a greater role in the teaching practice of the expanded group, higher education institutions should clarify the interplay between teaching behaviors and learning engagement, make teachers design blended teaching based on and targeted, focus on the effective integration of blended teaching design and teaching strategies for precise implementation, optimize the blended learning experience by enhancing students' self-efficacy and learning motivation, and thus improve learning effectiveness. To promote a fruitful reform of talent cultivation in adult academic education.

Introduction

The learning needs of diversified students after the expansion of higher education require higher education institutions to adopt a flexible and dynamic teaching mode, and the blended learning mode becomes the main way of teaching change. The characteristics of diversified students with adult roles and years of social life and work experience require that higher vocational education must consider the cultivation of adult education on the basis of the original school education and carry out learning activities adapted to social development in accordance with the learning needs of adult groups. The student-centered teaching theory is developed and constructed on the basis of humanistic teaching theory and constructivist teaching theory. This chapter will explain the development of the above theories and the distance education theories that support the realization of blended learning as well as their connotations, and further analyze the characteristics of adult education for diverse social students and the connotations of blended learning, in order to deepen the knowledge and understanding of the blended learning model for diverse students and lay the theoretical foundation for the subsequent research.

Humanistic learning theory

I. The development of humanistic thinking

The idea of Humanism (Humanism) originated from the philosophical consideration of what a person (Human Being) is. Protagoras, an ancient Greek scholar who first proposed the idea of humanism, believed that "man is the source of all things" and built the core of philosophical thought with "man" as the center for the first time.

"Protagoras' understanding of humanism highlights the subjectivity of human beings. Sokrates (Socrates) proposed that people can only deepen their knowledge of themselves through continuous self-reflection, emphasizing the active reflection and behavior of individuals and thus highlighting their subjectivity, which also has a profound influence on people's self-knowledge (Liu, Tie-fang, 2010). Plato (Plato) further propagated Sokrates' ideas and proposed that "The human mind is the source of knowing all things", formed a unique concept by integrating human reason, emotion and mind through the perspective of psychology, raised the essence of human nature from the potential inner to the level of consciousness, emphasized the importance of individual consciousness, and provided an important inspiration for the development of humanism. Aristotle (Aristotle), on the basis of individual consciousness put forward the idea that individuals should strive for their own situation, sublimated the awareness of human thinking to the understanding of value, and further elaborated the meaning of human subject position (Liu, Liang-Hua, 2012).

During the Renaissance in the West, the central position of human being was also highlighted, opposing feudal theism, celebrating the free spirit of human being, spreading the liberation of human personality, respecting and expressing the value of human interest, choice and individual existence, encouraging individual thought innovation in philosophy, literature and natural science, and showing the value and meaning of emphasizing "human discovery". The value and meaning of "human discovery" were emphasized. In the modern West, based on the Renaissance, human rationality and dignity were further promoted, and the independence and emancipation of human personality were advocated, showing the emphasis on human thinking and the meaning of human existence. (2005).

In the modern Western era, the emphasis on human thinking and the meaning of human existence has been shown. The Renaissance period preached the value and meaning of human existence and that human beings should be respected. Pascal proposed that "the dignity of man is thought", indicating the pursuit of independent human thought (Han Qingxiang and An-Yi Kang, 2005). Rousseau (Rousseau) emphasized the nature of human beings, characterized by the promotion and affirmation of human nature, and the development of humanistic thought was greatly promoted by Rousseau's treatise (Liu, Tie-fang, 2010). Hegel (Hegel) proposed from an epistemological point of view that man should be rational and active in his thinking, and that he should actively pursue the development of things. Feuerbach established "anthroposophical materialism" from the perspective of humanism, emphasizing that human reason and will, the inner being, belong to the essence of man, and that the natural property of man is that he has sensory thinking. With the development of modern capitalism in the West, modern humanistic philosophers, represented by Schopenhauer and Nietzsche, emphasized that the essence of human existence is the individual life, nature, and instincts of human beings, specifically the complete existence of the body, will, emotions, and activities

Through continuous improvement and development, education has been influenced by many aspects of humanistic teaching theory in the process of practice, and it has also been widely studied and applied. First of all, the orientation of the teaching objectives of humanistic teaching theory has changed. The focus of humanism is not only on the transmission of knowledge content, but also on promoting students' self-understanding and in-depth learning of knowledge, and emphasizing students' creativity and individual needs in the learning process. Humanistic teaching theory advocates a learning process of independent student research, emphasizes students' emotional engagement, and values students' own knowledge construction. Under conditions that focus on promoting the subjectivity of students' independent learning, educators should be able to create a favorable atmosphere and environment for students' independent learning, and be able to combine students' previously acquired knowledge with experiences that are linked to new knowledge and more stimulating for them to understand and think about new knowledge. Learning is the realization of individual self-needs, therefore educators are required to choose learning methods and forms of learning that are beneficial to students according to their individual characteristics in teaching, and to promote the cultivation of students with the plurality and openness of the learning process. Students' emotions and cognition, which are emphasized in humanistic learning theory, should be emphasized in the educational process (Jia, 2005). Educators should focus on students' cognitive and emotional input while creating a positive learning environment to improve students' overall physical and mental development. Second, the concept of "student-centered" humanism promotes the concept of student-centered instructional design. Rogers points out that teachers also need to build a good learning environment and classroom atmosphere in the process of instructional design, choose a more suitable teaching environment and process, and adopt a multi-method teaching approach to motivate students to learn actively (Zhu, 2015). Finally, based on an instructional design concept that fully values students' subjectivity, humanistic learning theory promotes students' need for self-learning and the process of independent inquiry learning. Although humanistic theory puts forward pedagogical requirements for educators in the teaching process that go beyond the transmission of knowledge as the core, its emphasis on students' self-directed learning also gives them a wide space for learning, and students themselves are faced with the requirement of learning transformation. Motivation and a good attitude toward learning are what students need to have to learn, as well as the strong will and self-management ability to drive learning so that they can effectively integrate learning and thus better utilize their own learning initiative.

Constructivist learning theory

I. Psychological development of constructivist learning theory

Constructivist (Constructivist) learning theory is a further development of learning theory from behavior to cognitivism, which originally arose on the basis of research on children's cognitive development and was first proposed by Piaget, a Swiss psychologist, and was considered that learning activities are a process of reprocessing and shaping based on students' original knowledge and experience (Chen, W. X., 2021). Based on the process of children's psychological development, Piaget's research pointed out that children grow up as a continuous interaction with their surroundings and continuously construct knowledge and feedback from the outside world as a way to accumulate and develop their cognition. Accordingly, he proposed the occurrence cognitive theory (Zhong Qiquan, 2006) for the study of children's cognitive development, in which knowledge is understood in terms of the interaction between internal and external factors. Piaget believes that knowledge does not come from the subject or the object, and that the extension of the original experience and knowledge structure is necessary to better acquire new knowledge, which also causes the original knowledge and experience structure to change, and that the process of forming new knowledge is in The process of forming new knowledge is gradually constructed in the process of interaction between the original experience and the new content. From this perspective, the essence of learning is also a process of discovery and understanding in which subjective knowledge and object things are mutually constructed.

Other scholars have further expanded on the nature and developmental factors of cognitive structure based on Piaget's developmental cognitive theory of constructivism, while scholars such as Kernberg and Katz have emphasized the key role played by individual agency in the process of cognitive structure construction (Ho, 1997). They proposed a triadic theory of intelligence consisting of components, experiences, and contexts of individual intelligence, and argued that differences in individual intelligence are due to different ways of processing external stimuli. kernberg et al.'s triadic theory of intelligence is a challenge to traditional cognitive psychology, more in line with contemporary developments in cognitive psychology, closer to life in terms of learning activities, and thus more comprehensive. Vyogotsgy emphasizes the role of conditions such as socio-cultural and historical context on the cognitive process in which students learn (Knouz, 2014).Vyogotsgy's research in the context of history and culture points out that people's learning and their own development are based on a certain social environment and historical and cultural context, and it emphasizes that the internalization process of individual learning is not only Vyogotsgy also further distinguishes between the real and potential levels of development of individual learning development. His research indicates that the real level is the final level of development that an individual can achieve when performing independent activities without external intervention, while the potential level is the final level of development that can be achieved with the help of multiple external individual interventions. According to Vyogotsgy, the area between these two levels is called the "zone of most recent development", which has also evolved into the "zone of most recent development" theory. To achieve better learning or developmental outcomes, teaching activities must be developmentally advanced. The results of this research reveal the developmental characteristics of the students and clearly indicate that learning activities consist of "training and reinforcement" that stimulate and shape the students' mental perceptions. It is important to understand the relationship between development and education at these two very different levels (Steve and Gale, 2002).

There are many schools of constructivist learning theory, which are rich in content and have different tendencies of theoretical development. These many different studies have extended and enriched the constructivist theory, provided theoretical support for the application of the theory to different types of teaching practice, and further provided practical references for the reform of teaching process and teaching environment.

Connotation of constructivist teaching theory

The traditional view of knowledge theory indicates that knowledge is the objective reflection of people's knowledge of the external world, and teaching is to present this reflection to students, and the drawbacks of this traditional knowledge teaching promote the proposal of constructivism. This view has raised questions because it does not reflect the internal process of students' learning of knowledge and does not reflect their own mastery and concrete application of what they have learned. Since the development of individuals' cognition of the world is closely related to their learning in reality, constructivism's cognition of individuals' experiences better clarifies the cognitive laws of individuals' performance in the learning process. "Assimilation is the process of integrating the content of external information factors into one's own cognitive system, while conformity is the process in which factors from the external environment influence the individual's cognitive structure to change in the same direction. The individual's assimilation and adaptation will reach a state of balance with the stimulating information from the external environment through the individual's self-adjustment, and it is based on the "balance-imbalance-new balance" formed by the new stimulating information that promotes the individual's knowledge enrichment and development (Du Chengming, 1999). Therefore, the constructivist theory emphasizes the continuous learning process to narrow the gap between oneself and the real life, and the

transfer of knowledge through perception and construction, which is an important critique and warning for the traditional offline classroom teaching, and also triggers the change of teaching.

Constructivist Learning Theory for Teaching Practice

Constructivism cuts into the teaching process of knowledge learning with a new ideology, inspiring most scholars to rethink their teaching theories and having a significant impact on the development of educational theory and teaching practice. Based on the traditional didactic concept, constructivist learning theory puts forward a new paradigm of teaching theory and practice, emphasizing the process of active construction of new knowledge by combining students' existing knowledge experience in the learning process.

First of all, constructivist learning theory indicates the subjectivity of students and their initiative in knowledge construction. The interactive premise of constructivism's old knowledge experience is to bring into play the key position of students as learning subjects, who are active participants in the acquisition and learning of new knowledge and active constructors of content mastery, and teachers should reflect the promotion and guarantee of students' constructive learning in the process of teaching design and teaching organization and implementation (Pan Yujin, 2000). The theory transforms the traditional teacher-centered ideological understanding of lecture-based teaching activities and advocates and promotes student-centered teacher-directed and heuristic teaching models. From the teacher's point of view, the idea is to change the traditional teacher-student role in teaching, highlighting the main position and initiative of students in the learning process. In the actual teaching process, we should focus on promoting students' participation in the learning initiative while paying attention to guiding students' existing knowledge experience, not just rely on content indoctrination type knowledge teaching method, but also set teaching tasks based on students' own experience comprehensive consideration, guiding students' active inquiry-based learning based on existing experience, so as to more profoundly grasp the actual problem-solving ability. At the same time, teachers can consider flexible and diversified and adaptive teaching methods to stimulate students to learn dialectically with reverse and questioning thinking, to change mechanical learning from listening to lectures to active participation and inquiry-based learning, and to transform teachers from controlling lecturing "lecturers" to "tutors" of students' learning process. The teacher is transformed from a "lecturer" who controls the lecture to a "tutor" for the students' learning process, who guides the learning in terms of learning methods and can trigger the students to construct deeper meanings for the known knowledge in terms of learning contents.

Second, constructivist teaching theory focuses on the interactivity between students and teachers and between old and new knowledge in the learning process. Constructivism emphasizes the role embodied by the cooperation that occurs between learning interactions, and this cooperative interaction is reflected between students and teachers, students and students, students and the environment, and also between the turnover and deepening of new and old knowledge of students, and this interaction also reflects students' active participation in the process of knowledge learning and meaning construction. Therefore, collaborative teaching is advocated in specific teaching practices because the learning exchange between teachers and students or students facilitates the realization of knowledge construction (Ding Rui et al. , 2019). Cooperative learning approaches can be adopted in specific teaching practices through activities such as group discussions and cooperative social research, where teachers enhance student-student, group-student, and student-group communication and coordination in activities to make students view problems more comprehensively and diversified.

Finally, constructivist learning theory focuses on the important role of the formation of a good learning environment. The learning environment includes not only the real space that makes up the teaching activity, but also the specific teaching context, communication and meaning construction during the teaching process, and good learning contexts help students communicate and cooperate with each other (Zhang and Chen, Q., 1996). Traditional offline classroom teaching focuses on the direct transfer of knowledge and ignores unstructured knowledge and students' life experiences. Constructivist learning theory constructs real or simulated learning situations that fit the actual practice, creates appropriate situations based on students, focuses on unstructured knowledge and students' existing experiences, and realizes the construction of students' knowledge. In the specific teaching process, the learning content should be integrated with specific contexts, and intercommunication and integration between different disciplines are advocated. Teachers should provide students with a large number of cases and appropriately use modern teaching media to create an interactive learning environment for students, forming a learning atmosphere in which students actively explore and actively construct, so as to promote students to regularly think about establishing the inner connection and interaction between old and new knowledge in the learning process, giving full play to the role of bridge and ladder of students' inner knowledge structure, so as to improve students' use of old In this way, students can improve their ability to use old knowledge to deepen the construction of new knowledge and solve specific problems.

At the core of constructivist learning theory is the proposal that students are active learners of knowledge as constructors of meaning, which provides a new interpretation of knowledge, learning and teaching. Although the viewpoint of constructivism breaks the deadlock of the active role of students in teaching and learning, some

of its views still have obvious subjectivism and boundary restrictions. The theory cannot solve all the problems of teaching practice as a whole, nor can it completely replace the existing teaching and learning theories in terms of popularity, but the meaningfulness of knowledge-constructing learning favorably reveals the activeness of the learning subject, and provides an opportunity to guide students to actively construct knowledge, and provide a referenceable idea for in-depth research on the mechanism, ways and strategies of knowledge construction.

Theory of Distance Education

I. The concept of distance education

Since the 1960s, some foreign scholars have defined distance education, and some representative ones are German scholars such as Dorman, Peters, and Moore and Holmberg (Ding Xingfu, 2001). Dorman pointed out that distance education is a form of student-led learning using distance communication technology, which is different from the "face-to-face" education of teachers and students. According to Peters (1973), distance education is a method of imparting knowledge through the media by means of technology and an industrialized form of teaching that allows for mass reproduction of teaching materials for synchronous teaching. Moore (1977), on the other hand, sees distance learning as a form of instruction that is implemented separately from the act of learning through electronic, mechanical, and other means, including situations where there are students receiving live face-to-face education. Holmberg (1997) considers distance education in which the teacher and the student are in different locations and the student can plan a type of instructional activity under the fixed and discontinuous guidance of the teacher.

These definitions specify the characteristics of distance education from different perspectives and define the basic concepts of distance education with different theories and perspectives. In a literal sense, distance education is typically characterized as a non-face-to-face, spatially and temporally distant "distance" educational activity. In terms of technical attributes, distance education is an educational activity developed in response to the needs of social development and the popularity of digital technology. According to the new characteristics and trends of modern distance education, domestic scholar Ding Xingfu (2001) defines distance education as all kinds of educational activities in which teachers and students are relatively separated in time and space, and their connections are made through educational communication media resources. On the basis of Ding Xingfu's research, Li Kang (2003) pointed out that distance education is an educational activity implemented by teaching resources with the help of new media technology that breaks through the limitation of time and space, and it has specific means of information transmission and communication, as well as educational resources and corresponding educational management system and methods that adapt to the distance education method. Compared with traditional typical education methods, distance education has the following characteristics.

Morphologically, non-contact teaching is the core expression of distance education, and most people tend to confuse the concepts of both distance teaching and distance education triggered by this. Li Kang (2003) also points out the difference between distance education and distance learning, arguing that they are concepts at different levels. Distance learning is subjectively classified as a category of teaching behavior between two types of groups, teachers and students, and is a way of teaching, and distance education covers distance learning in terms of content, but distance learning is the core of distance education in terms of teaching organization. Therefore, in terms of teaching performance, the effectiveness of distance education is often argued by the effect of distance learning. In essence, distance learning is a way of teaching activity that realizes knowledge transmission in teaching and learning time and space separation by means of information technology, and the teaching organization process includes elements such as teaching resources, teaching design and offline and online teaching methods. Compared with the teaching situation in offline classrooms, distance learning presents unique characteristics.

Basic theories of distance education

The theory of distance education is a systematic elaboration of the characteristics and laws of non-contact education formed by using information technology such as mobile Internet and the new generation of digital technology. Since the 1960s, a large number of domestic and foreign scholars have put forward various views on the research of distance education and formed a large number of research results respectively. By sorting out the existing researches, this study summarizes the corresponding basic theories of distance education, as shown in Table 2.4.

The theory of autonomous learning emerged in the 1960s and 1970s, which reveals the problem of students' autonomy and self-regulated learning in distance education and points out that students' self-learning control in the learning process is the key to the realization and development of distance education. This theory gives great insight into the importance of cultivating students' autonomy and independence in distance education, and reflects that distance education is a way to realize personalization of education and diversification of learning. Although the theory reveals the importance of independent learning, it neglects to some extent the importance of the teaching aspect. The perceived natural increase with individual maturity in learning autonomy also negates the educational development role of autonomy.

Conclusion

The theory of industrialization of distance education was proposed by Peter (1967), which explains the technical characteristics of distance education in terms of industrial production, considering traditional classroom education as a pre-industrial form and distance education realized by network communication technology that can expand the audience group across time and space as a working form. This theory makes us realize that traditional education cannot meet the requirements of modern society in terms of scale and efficiency for mass production with high quality of workers. From the viewpoint of industrialization, the emergence and development of distance education is a form of education that breaks through the limitations of traditional handicraft industry, and differs from the original classroom teaching in which the overall teaching activities are concentrated. The workflow of teaching resources in the process of dissemination is "assembly line" type. However, the theory of industrialization of distance education overemphasizes the scale impact of information technology on educational activities, but ignores other elements that constitute distance education other than technological factors. After all, educational activities cannot be contrasted with production activities, and the laws of production activities cannot be applied to the laws of education, thus the concept of industrialization can be explained in understanding the technological formation of distance education, but it is inappropriate to understand the overall teaching and learning activities of distance education in its entirety in this way.

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Author Information

Hua Tian

International College, Krirk University Thailand

Yan Jun Song

International College, Krirk University Thailand
